

EFFICIENT POST-MACHINING AND AUTOMATED REPAIR PREPARATION USING ADAPTIVE MACHINING TECHNOLOGY

Dr. Claus Bremer

BCT GmbH, Carlo-Schmid-Allee 3, 44263 Dortmund, Germany,
Email: c.bremer@bct-online.de, web page: www.bct-online.de

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ABSTRACT

Components made from fibre-reinforced plastics (FRP) exhibit a unique set of properties not only mechanically, but also during manufacturing, reworking and repair. State-of-the-art processes designed for isotropic materials such as metals cannot be used in many scenarios or have drawbacks when used on composites. In particular, deviations from a component's nominal shape play a decisive role when working with these materials.

With the quickly growing market for structural components made from FRP, the often manual state-of-the-art processes for the manufacturing, reworking and repair of such components are reaching their limits. Automated processes must be implemented in order to meet the steadily growing requirements with respect to process times and stability.

This paper focusses on the application of geometrically adaptive machining processes throughout the life cycle of composite components. The implementation of adaptive machining in composite manufacturing, reworking and repair is addressed. An overview of current developments and the future potential of this technology are outlined.

1. INTRODUCTION

Throughout the manufacturing, reworking and repair of FRP components, machining processes are used for various applications. During all these processes, unavoidable deviations from nominal shape play a decisive role. Because most composite components vary to some degree from their nominal shape, fixed NC programs cannot be used for the automation of such processes. Additionally, the sensitivity of composite structures to unwanted damage of fibre layers requires a machining process to follow the actual part geometry very precisely.

Manual processes are still considered state of the art for many of these processes – but are also extremely time-consuming [1]. To improve the overall economy of use for FRP structures, automated processes are a must.

Geometrically adaptive machining technology has been used successfully for decades in the manufacture and repair of aero-engine and turbine components [2]. This technology has now been transferred and adapted to the needs of the composite sector. Tests have been conducted successfully on both stationary and mobile machines. A specialized 5-axis mobile milling machine and the corresponding processes have been developed for on-aircraft composite repair.

This paper focusses on the reworking of fibre-reinforced plastic (FRP) components during manufacturing as well as the repair of such structures while in service. It gives a summary of adaptive machining in the field of composites and showcases achieved results as well as current developments for all interested readers. It shall be shown that the technology of geometrically adaptive machining has been transferred successfully to composites applications and can be used for the efficient repair and reworking of composite structures.

2. EXPERIMENTATION

2.1 Bonding properties of machined FRP surfaces

Preliminary studies have shown that milling is more effective than laser ablation and water jetting for composite material removal [3]. To achieve perfect preparation of the repair area, all aspects of scarfing by milling must be examined meticulously. Various milling strategies and new milling tools have been developed and optimized. To achieve a bondable FRP surface which is able to carry loads, macroscopic geometric precision is needed in combination with minor damage of microscopic dimensions.

Figure 1 shows a milled stepped scarf in a carbon-fibre-reinforced plastic (CFRP) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of a milled step displaying the desirable properties described above.

Figure 1: Stepped scarf in a CFRP plate and SEM image of a milled step

2.2 Measuring and scanning

Every adaptive machining process starts with the capture of component geometry. One of the goals of this development was to be able to machine a repair scarf without any prior knowledge of a part's nominal geometry, e.g. through CAD data. Hence a precise measuring process lies at the core of the adaptive milling process.

2.2.1 Measuring and scanning technologies

There is a wide variety of tactile measuring methods and optical scanning systems available for this purpose – from the classic machine-integrated tactile probe to the robot-guided structured light scanner.

During the design of an adaptive machining system and process, the specified accuracies and the geometrical task description are decisive. For large-scale CFRP structures, which are to be milled in three dimensions over their entire surface, optical scanners are the devices of choice.

A second important aspect is the decision as to whether geometrical data capture should be integrated into the NC machine or whether a separate scanning system would be more advantageous. If separate units are used for scanning and for NC machining, additional expenses and effort may be required for materials handling and possibly for fixtures and component referencing as well.

In general, machine-integrated scanning is the preferred system configuration.

2.2.2 Optical scanning on NC machines

While an overwhelming variety of scanning technologies is available for separate scanning units, the possibilities for machine-integrated geometrical data capture are currently limited largely to touch trigger probes.

To remedy this situation, a solution has been developed that permits 6-axis scanning with line scanners in 5-axis NC machines. Here the spindle is used as the sixth controlled axis. With this solution process-integrated and machine-integrated scanning of components can be realized.

As the laser line scanner has a relatively small focus area, a precise distance to the surface to be scanned must be maintained in order to attain precise measurements. To generate the scanning path, a rough geometrical model of the component is needed.

A point laser is used to detect the topology of the area, from which the adaptive milling software calculates a tool path for the laser line scanner. In a next step the line scanner is used to detect the 3D geometry of the component with a high degree of accuracy.

To further enhance the accuracy and data reliability of the scanning process, a method was developed to compensate for the influence exerted by the optical properties of the scanned surface. To achieve this, an algorithm calculates multiple passes of the laser line scanner on the same surface, but from different angles. Through the input of multiple data points for the same surface, the algorithm can then calculate the influence of the surface properties and compensate for them. Additionally, this scanning method allows for a consistency check of the gathered data to prevent damage to the component occurring through errors in the scanning data.

For easy-to-scan surfaces, a red-light laser line scanner is used. This scanning equipment is sufficient for most CFRP applications. For fully automated operation with tool-changing capabilities, a wireless version is used. For surfaces that are more difficult to scan, an enhanced blue-light laser line scanner is preferable. This scanning method has shown greatly improved scanning precision compared with a red-light laser scanner operating on semi-transparent surfaces such as GFRP.

Figure 2: Line scanning as part of a mobile milling machine on a composite helicopter fuselage

2.3 Geometrically adaptive machining

Based on the data obtained by scanning, an adaptive machining path can be calculated. This process can be separated into two main process steps: calculation of the part geometry and calculation and adaptation of an NC milling program.

2.3.1 Geometrical adaptation

The scanning data collected in previous process steps constitutes the basis for adaptive processing of the component. First a 3D surface model, reproducing the actual geometry of the damaged area, is generated from the scan data. The nominal CAD geometry may be taken into account for this but is not actually necessary.

As a next step, the target geometry is calculated. Multiple factors can be considered when calculating this geometry, which describes the shape of the part after milling. Besides the actual part geometry, the nominal part geometry and other parameters for the geometry can be used to influence the target geometry. These can include, for example, factors such as minimum wall thickness or aerodynamic parameters which must be maintained to ensure the functionality of the finished part.

2.3.2 Adaptation of NC programs

Various methods can then be used to generate a master milling program. This master milling program describes the process without reference to actual component geometry. Among other possibilities, it can be calculated on the basis of the parameters input by the operator, figures taken from a database, or the scanned part geometry and the determined target geometry.

The 3-axis master milling program is then transferred to the 3D surface geometry of the scanned part. The geometrically adapted milling programs have 5 axes and run parallel to the contours of the actual geometry of the damaged area.

The final result of the adaptation process is an NC program adapted to the actual (i.e. measured or scanned) geometry. In contrast to a fixed NC program, the milling tool thus follows the actual component contours and not a fixed path. To calculate the geometrically adapted NC program, the tool centre point is computed according to the displacement of the corresponding tool touch point. This is possible through the knowledge of the actual part geometry as well as tool geometry and orientation.

This step eliminates the need for machine-internal tool calculations and offsets. The NC code for a point which is to be milled can rather consist of a single line of code, making the adaptive milling process compatible with virtually all NC machines and independent of path strategies or machine technologies.

2.4 Automated scarfing for composite repair

Based on the adaptation process described above, a repair process for FRP components was developed. The adaptation software package runs on a PC and is connected via LAN to the NC control of the multi-axis machine.

Within the software package for composite repair, a patch geometry generator was implemented. If no scarfing geometry is imported, it allows for the calculation of a patch geometry as needed.

Both stepped and tapered scarfings can be generated, as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 3: Generic algorithm for the generation of nominal NC tool paths for stepped and tapered scarfings of any shape

Based on the calculated geometry or an imported geometry, the master milling program is created. As described in the previous chapters, this master milling program is then adapted to the part geometry, machine kinematics and transferred to the machine for milling.

Some examples of scarfing geometries and their application on FRP components are shown below.

Figure 4: Circular scarfing on commercial aircraft fuselage skin

Figure 5: Elliptical scarfing on a helicopter rotor blade

Figure 6: Rectangular scarfing on a helicopter fuselage

Tests were also conducted for geometrically challenging repair applications, where standard scarfing geometries cannot be applied. Damages near the edges of FRP components (e.g. trailing edges) were a common problem. Frequently, the available surface area is not large enough to accommodate a uniformly shaped patch.

A special scarfing geometry was developed that satisfies the structural requirements in these areas while maintaining minimum material thicknesses and taking account of other factors. Such scarfing geometries are shown in the figure below.

Figure 7: Special scarfing geometries for boundary areas

2.5 Other applications of adaptive machining in composites

The necessity to compensate for geometrical variances does not only occur in the repair and reworking of composite components. One other situation in which precise surfaces are needed is the joining of composite components. Currently, the often-required manual shimming process for bonding CFRP components constitutes a bottleneck in the production of such components [4]. To achieve minimum weight and maximum structural performance, the goal is a bond which is as thin as possible.

This is extremely difficult to achieve, owing to the aforementioned shape deviations displayed by composite components. For this reason, shims are commonly used to permit bonding of such components.

Adaptive machining and measuring processes can be utilized in two different ways to optimize the bonding process. One of these is scanning the two surfaces to be bonded, and then calculating a shim geometry which can then be milled, created with additive manufacturing, or realized with any other suitable technology.

The other approach is sacrificial machining, where one or both surfaces to be bonded are manufactured with some additional material. When this material thickness is known and both surfaces are scanned, it is possible to calculate the ideal matching geometry, which can then be milled into the components, as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 8: Sacrificial machining for optimized bond thickness

As described in previous chapters, limitations and requirements with respect to the geometry of the shim or the components can also be considered. For example, the maximum milling depth into the components can be defined to ensure structural integrity, or a minimum wall thickness can be specified.

2.6 Additional process steps

As mentioned in chapter 2.1, the surface properties of a FRP component are crucial to allow structural bonding and ensure sufficient mechanical properties. Many different technologies have been developed and used to improve bonding conditions. While mechanical processes such as milling are perfectly suited to remove large amounts of material efficiently as well as to provide a mechanically suitable surface for bonding, the chemical properties of the achieved surface are not ideal for this purpose. Advantageous processes for chemical surface preparation include, for example, plasma or UV treatment. Hence a combination of milling for material removal and plasma processes for surface activation are considered ideal for reliable bonded repairs. [3]

Tests have been conducted successfully to integrate atmospheric plasma after the milling process to ensure ideal bonding conditions.

Figure 9: Atmospheric plasma being used to improve surface properties for a bonded repair

3. RESULTS

With the use of adaptive machining and adequate milling technology, the post-machining, reworking and repair of composites can be greatly accelerated. Figure 10 shows a milled scarf in a composite fuselage structure; the scarf had been milled in about ten minutes. By hand, such a repair scarf would have taken several hours and the quality would strongly depend on the person doing the scarfing. Furthermore, automation allows for improved reproducibility of surface qualities.

Figure 10: Milled scarf in a CFRP fuselage [5]

New geometries for fibre-orientated joints and repairs are becoming possible. Figure 11 shows a fibre-orientated scarf in a CFRP plate. With such improved scarfing geometries, repair areas could shrink since the bonding area is reduced significantly without losing structural strength.

Figure 11: Fibre-orientated scarf in a CFRP plate [5]

4. CONCLUSIONS

During all phases of FRP manufacturing and repair, deviations of composite components from nominal shape play a decisive role. Adaptive machining compensates for both individual deviations from nominal shape and inaccurate clamping positions. This makes it possible to automate geometrically critical NC processes such as the post-machining, reworking and repair of composite structures.

The process of adaptive machining in composite applications has been successfully demonstrated on both mobile and stationary machines. Additional steps such as surface treatment have been integrated and tested successfully, facilitating subsequent process steps.

It can thus be said that adaptive machining demonstrates great potential for improved efficiency and quality in the post-machining, reworking and repair of composite components [6].

5. OUTLOOK

Studies are currently underway to realize and prove the applicability of additional technologies for incorporation into the adaptive machining process chain. Such technologies include, for example, 3D non-destructive testing with ultrasound or the integration of cutting heads for prepreg. Fibre-orientated repairs like those as shown in Figure 11 are also being tested to assess their applicability.

As the geometry of the scarfing is known very precisely, it is possible to export the geometry even before milling the scarf. From this geometry the required repair layers can be calculated. This could, for example, permit the manufacturing of a repair patch while the milling process is in progress, further improving the efficiency of the overall process.

Other studies currently being conducted are investigating the integration of industrial robots into the machining process, either as a handling system for a mobile milling machine or as the milling end effector itself.

6. REFERENCES

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